

Cancer patients – in the past and at present

Paulina Zachara-Kierońska¹ ABCDEF, Magdalena Pieniążek² ABCDEF, Marcin Zieliński³ ABCDEF

¹Krakow Higher School of Health Promotion,

²Jagiellonian University Medical College, Faculty of Health Sciences,

³Krzeszowice Rehabilitation Centre,

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Abstract

The paper aims to present the approach to neoplastic diseases over the years. Cancer is currently the second most common cause of death in Poland. The development of medicine has offered increasing opportunities to explore and analyse the human body, its structure and components. Nevertheless, the number of cancer patients is still on the rise. Important aspects include not only prevention and treatment, but also all appropriate measures to assist patients in their recovery. Scientists have presented numerous theories concerning the emergence of cancer groups and their current significant increase in the incidence rate. However, it still remains an issue that requires further examination. The knowledge about cancer patients is not merely related to the treatment method that can be offered in each particular case, but also to the types of actions that should be avoided to ensure that patients' health condition does not deteriorate.

Keywords: *cancer patient, the history of medicine, oncological package*

1. Introduction

The purpose of the present paper is to describe the changes that have occurred in the approach to and understanding of cancer over the years. The development of medicine has provided increasingly sophisticated methods and tools for gaining insight into the human body and exploring its anatomy in more detail. Initially, the human body was known to consist of organs, which were later subdivided into tissues. Then, after the invention of the microscope, they were discovered to be made up of a huge number of cells. Today, we know that the cell itself is a complicated unit and some diseases may be caused by abnormal structures of such cellular products as enzymes or receptors. By extension, diseases can also result from abnormalities in the genetic material.

There are numerous records in literature concerning cancer as a "man-made" disease of developed countries. Some researchers suggest that cancer was non-existent in ancient times [1]. On the other hand, this statement sparked a major discussion amongst the scientific community, and subsequent authors presented their evidence that cancer is not at all a disease created by the "contemporary world" [2]. However, this does not undermine the fact that, prior to starting work with cancer patients, it is recommended – out of respect for the patients themselves and for one's own knowledge – to become familiar with the data concerning medicine hundreds of years ago. While working on these issues, it is crucial to realise and understand the complicated and life-threatening

nature of cancer, which often makes it clear in a brutal manner about how huge the cancer-related challenge is for today's medicine.

The number of cancer patients is constantly growing. Important aspects include not only prevention and treatment, but also all relevant measures to assist patients in their recovery. A comprehensive method of fighting cancer encompasses the following: epidemiology and cancer registry; planning and controlling research; teaching, health education and organisation of permanent social struggle with neoplastic diseases; prevention, detection, diagnosis and treatment of cancer patients; psychophysical rehabilitation and terminal care; maintenance of continuous documentation and permanent care of cancer patients until the end of their life as well as socioeconomic assessment of the results of all the activities within oncology. Research and clinical practice are closely linked in the area of fighting cancer, and the ultimate objective of this activity is to reduce prevalence and increase the number of cured patients, and hence to decrease cancer mortality. Even though the importance of rehabilitation has been stressed for centuries, it is a relatively new approach in this field of medicine. It is currently becoming more widespread to talk about physical activity requiring more effort or even sport in the context of cancer patients. Until a few decades ago, there was quite the opposite trend and patients were, in no circumstances, recommended to get involved in physical activity. Nowadays, there is a discussion about health coaching or the use of applications to support

treatment – all intended to save the patients' precious time. Nowadays, great emphasis is placed on the issue of the patients' quality of life, which was completely disregarded in the past.

2. The history of oncology – selected issues from the 20th and the 21st centuries

In the 1960s, Frei and Freireich analysed the cerebrospinal fluid of leukaemia patients. They were shocked to find out that millions of cells proliferate very rapidly to gradually occupy the entire area of the brain tissue. A bone marrow biopsy revealed no evidence of cancer. In the meantime, the leukemic cells had already attacked the nervous system (headaches, dementia, and sudden death). This was caused by certain defence mechanisms of the body, which simply boosted the development of leukaemia. The blood-brain barrier serves to prevent foreign substances and chemical compounds from entering the brain (protection against poisons). The component drugs of the VAMP regimen (a combination therapy for the treatment of leukaemia with high doses of vincristine, amethopterin, 6-mercaptopurine and prednisone) were not “allowed” into the brain. As a result, cancer cells could easily invade the only area in the body not accessible to chemotherapy. This was a period during which physicians imagined cancer as a single disease entity. Therefore, they searched for a single universal cure for all cancer types.

In 1962, British chemists from Imperial Chemical Industries (ICI) obtained a chemical referred to as ICI 46474 – tamoxifen (an organic chemical compound that exhibits anti-oestrogenic action), which was originally conceived to be a contraceptive pill. However, it was found that the new substance, designed to act as a powerful oestrogen stimulant, had the opposite effect than desired. The failure of the “fertility control” team turned out to be a kind of success in oncology. Mary Cole, who was in charge of a ward with female patients suffering from advanced disseminated breast cancer, was determined enough to attempt to use even an unsuccessful contraceptive. In 1969, the results of a clinical trial showed that breast tumours had shrivelled visibly, lung metastases shrunk, ostealgia (bone pain) subsided and lymph nodes softened. For the first time ever, a drug was designed to target a specific receptor of a cancer cell. This resulted in both remissions and metastases. Later, it was discovered that cells exhibiting oestrogen receptor expression were capable of binding tamoxifen. As an oestrogen antagonist, tamoxifen deactivated reactivity to oestrogen, thereby inhibiting cell growth. ER-negative cells had no receptor to bind the drug and were therefore not resistant to it. A decision was made to use medication capable of inhibiting cancer in stage IV in

less advanced forms of the disease. This led to the application of the CMP regimen in cancer treatment, based on cyclophosphamide – a mustard gas derivative, methotrexate – a variety of amethopterin, fluorouracil – a DNA synthesis inhibitor. The cause of cancer still remained unknown and the concepts trying to explain it obscure.

Three years earlier, in 1966, Peyton Rous received the Nobel Prize for his viral theory of cancer (he admitted that the theory needed further elaboration, at the same time rejecting the idea that cancer might be caused by cell mutations). Going back another three years to 1963, we are confronted with the Kaplan's theory, which maintained that the nature of early-stage cancer developing locally is often different from that of disseminated cancer – even when it concerns the same form of the disease. These insights led to a careful adjustment of concrete therapies to specific forms and stages of cancer (the search for a one-size-fits-all cure was abandoned).

At the end of the 1960s, there was a significant change in the patient-doctor relationship. It was understood that the patient's own body may feed cancer. Huggins developed his own treatment method, which he called “chemical castration”. The administration of steroids failed to cure cancer. On the contrary, it resulted in remission, followed by the patient's resistance to hormone therapy. However, it proved that in order to achieve remission (lasting for even a few months), it is not necessary to administer a substance which is poisonous to all the patient's cells (cisplatin, mustard gas). Unfortunately, prevention still has not been indicated as a component of pre-cancer treatment. Barry Marshall gave a very general description of the treatment provided to one of his female patients suffering from gastritis with pre-neoplastic foci: “You are stressed, my dear. In fact, you are well. We will prescribe you antidepressants”. He did not suggest implementing any preventive measures.

In 1974, an English nurse, Cicely Saunders, noticed that oncologists were far too preoccupied with combating cancer to be able to get involved in the care of individual patients. Therefore, she decided to put an emphasis on the cooperation with other specialists, including psychiatrists, anaesthesiologists, geriatricians, physiotherapists and neurologists. Through her efforts to promote palliative care, Saunders expressed her objection to treatment at all costs. So far, treatment had been tantamount to action, while care had been regarded as inaction. Patients were refused pain-relieving opiates (morphine). Halsted, a famous Boston surgeon, stubbornly claimed that “if surgery is withheld, the sufferer is doomed to opiate addiction, physical deterioration or even suicide”. However, this statement was hypocrisy because the doctor himself was addicted to cocaine and morphine. In the same year, the director of the National Cancer Institute (NCI) spoke about a

three-pronged approach to cancer, including treatment, rehabilitation and care. However, not a single word was uttered about anti-cancer prophylaxis or early detection of cancer.

The results of the observations carried out in the 1980s proved that the Nobel Prize winner had been wrong. The research by Ames demonstrated that carcinogenicity is correlated with mutagenicity [3].

As mentioned at the beginning of the paper, Professor Rosalie David of the Centre for Biomedical Egyptology at the University of Manchester and Michael Zimmerman of Villanova University in Pennsylvania underline, in their recent publications, that all cancer is man-made. By analysing the tissues of nearly a thousand Egyptian mummies, predominantly of ordinary people who had died at the age of 25-50 years, it was possible to find only five cases of neoplasia, of which only one was malignant. The evidence provided by Egyptian written sources concerning neoplasms proved to be rare and insignificant as well. Professor Zimmerman stresses that it is impossible for neoplastic traces not to have survived until today, because the experiment conducted confirmed that mummified tumours are actually better preserved than healthy tissues. According to the author, it cannot be stated either that ancient people lived too short to develop cancer, which nowadays affects primarily the elderly. Some mummies were found to have suffered from atherosclerosis and osteoporosis. Therefore, if Egyptians lived long enough to develop these diseases, they also should have been affected by cancer. Furthermore, the pair of scientists found no cases of cancer in the mummies of children [1].

Joachim Schüz argues that cancer affects mostly patients in older age groups. "90% of all cancer cases in men occur after the age of 50 years. Scientists who will examine the bodies of a thousand contemporary men who have died before 50, will also find no cancers at all", claims Dr Schüz. The absence of cancer in ancient children is not a good piece of evidence for him. Bone cancer is relatively common in the youngest of patients, but it still affects only one in 10 thousand children. Therefore, it would be necessary to examine 10 thousand child mummies in order to find, with a little bit of luck, one case of cancer [2].

Dr Kat Arney of Cancer Research UK emphasises that cancers are caused by numerous environmental factors, such as ultraviolet sun rays, natural radiation from the radioactive elements found in rocks, including radon, or viruses (for instance, the hepatitis virus can lead to liver cancer, while human papilloma virus (HPV) – to cervical cancer) [2].

Last year, the prestigious medical journal entitled *The Lancet Oncology* presented the results of the research by British scientists from the Public Health England Cancer

Research. They indicate that more than half of chemotherapy patients died from the therapy rather than the cancer itself. Chemotherapeutic drugs do not distinguish between cancer and normal cells (thereby killing both). Mature cancer cells change their metabolic pathway from aerobic to anaerobic (as a result of fermentation). It turned out that chemotherapy kills cancer cells that burn glucose and not those that ferment it. This means additional amounts of glucose for aggressive cells. As a result, they do not have to share it with other (healthy) cells and can proliferate more easily [4].

3. Cancer patients nowadays

Current forecasts indicate that the number of patients with cancer diagnosed over the preceding five years will reach approximately 75 million in 2030. Cancer affects not only the physical state of patients but also, to a significant extent, their psychological well-being. Medical progress in the field of oncology has been focused on methods that will allow for increasingly earlier detection of cancer, successful treatment and the subsequent recovery of the patient. Depending on the effects it exerts on the human body, the treatment of malignant neoplasms can be categorised into local and systemic (overall). In terms of the moment at which systemic treatment is administered, one can distinguish pre-operative and post-operative treatment. Based on the target of the therapy, it can be classified either as radical or symptomatic. Chemotherapy is the most effective way to eradicate cancerous cells. However, it also affects the general condition of patients. The drugs used in chemotherapy are non-selective and destroy healthy cells as well, particularly those that divide more rapidly than others, for instance hair cells and the cells found in the oral cavity, the gastro-intestinal tract or the bone marrow. The side-effects of chemotherapy can vary from mild to serious, depending on the type of regimen used and the patient's individual response. Radiotherapy is painless and does not make the patient radioactive. However, it can also produce some side effects. They depend on the site of the irradiated tumour and are usually limited to the irradiated field only. In some cases, radio- and/or chemotherapy are combined with surgery [5, 6].

Physiotherapy is now commonly used in almost every field of medicine. Unfortunately, in the case of oncology, a problem arises when patients start to treat their disease as a death sentence. The issues of paramount importance in this regard concern the moment of the diagnosis and the physician's skilful guidance offered to patients. Rehabilitation, when introduced before, in the course of or after completion of the treatment, may be extremely beneficial for the patients. However, it is still frequently ignored. The universality of physiotherapy in oncology means that

it should be equally available to each cancer patient, irrespective of the type, severity or selected method of treatment. Particular stress should be laid on physiotherapy administered prior to cancer treatment, which contributes to reducing the risk of complications and disorders, while increasing the chances of faster recovery. It should also be noted that cancer patients should often receive rehabilitation from the moment of diagnosis, though their hospitalisation, until the end of their life. It is recommended that rehabilitation encompass all aspects of their life – medical, psychosocial and professional. This should minimise the relapse of functional disorders, which are still dangerous years after completion of therapy [7].

Quick oncology diagnostics is currently the only National Health Fund (NFZ) programme dedicated solely to cancer patients. Other medical services, such as medical transport, rehabilitation, orthopaedic equipment, drug reimbursement and pain management outpatient clinics are available on an equal basis to all patients not having additional entitlements (e.g. War Veterans, Honorary Volunteer Blood Donors, Meritorious Transplant Donors and employees of plants manufacturing asbestos-containing materials).

On the website dedicated to the changes introduced by the Minister of Health under the oncological package, we can read, “Cancer patients (...) must receive special care. Time is of essence in this case. Whether or not a patient with malignancy survives is primarily dependent on the disease being detected at the earliest stage possible.”

There is also information that “... the new organisational solution aims to efficiently and quickly guide the patient through different stages of diagnosis and treatment. The Quick Oncological Therapy is not a healthcare programme within the meaning of the Act of August 27, 2004 on healthcare services financed from public funds (Dz.U. [Journal of Laws] from 2008, No. 164, Item 1027, as amended). It is intended for all patients with suspected or diagnosed malignancy. Neither the Ministry of Health nor the Polish National Health Fund (NFZ) qualifies patients for participation in the Quick Oncological Therapy programme.” The Quick Oncological Therapy solution (Figure 1) has been in force since January 1, 2015.

Fig. 1. Quick Oncological Therapy [8]

The authors of the project provided for shortening the total time of diagnostic procedures to exclude or confirm cancer from 9 weeks in 2015 to 7 weeks in 2017. The programme is addressed to patients with suspected malignancy and those undergoing oncological treatment. A general practitioner (GP) refers such patients to consultants and issues the so-called Cancer Diagnosis and Treatment Card (DiLO) [8].

In fact, consultant gynaecologists, pulmonologists and oncologists cannot issue the DiLO Card to patients with suspected cancer. The suspicion needs to be confirmed by test results. By contrast, General Practitioners can issue the DiLO Card based on a mere suspicion. It should be pointed out that patients are privileged (short waiting times for examinations, separate queues at the reception desk) until their cancer diagnosis is confirmed. Upon confirmation, the DiLO Card becomes inactive and cancer patients share the same queue and the same appointment dates with consultants as other patients. Patients who have suffered a relapse after a period of remission are not eligible for shorter appointment waiting times either. If a patient with laryngeal cancer is additionally found to have developed colorectal cancer, then the treatment will be applied to the laryngeal cancer only, as envisaged in the DiLO Card. Due to the ongoing treatment for the first cancer, the patient cannot undergo any diagnostic tests for the second type of cancer. The cooperation between the coordinator and other healthcare professionals is often not meaningful. It commonly happens that the absence of a physician's stamp (as acknowledgement of his/her consent) or the lack of clear indication concerning further diagnostic measures prevents patients from being registered in the right specialist outpatient clinic. For example, there are a few practices operating within a specialist urology outpatient clinic. If patients want to schedule an appointment at a urology outpatient clinic under the DiLO Card (a separate practice), they cannot do it without written consent signed and stamped by a physician (despite the indication in the DiLO Card) [8].

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Health from 2015, there are 13 highly specialised services that are currently refunded, including: transplantation of the liver, heart and lungs, operations for heart defects and the thoracic aorta with extracorporeal circulation. Bone marrow transplantation is not refunded by the National Health Fund in Poland [9].

Prof. dr hab. Mirosław Ząbek, a neurosurgeon, along with its team from the Bródnowski Hospital in Warsaw, is trying to convince the Ministry of Health and the National Health Fund to create the first brain gene therapy centre in Poland. The gene therapy method could be used in the chemotherapy of brain tumours [10]. In Great Britain, such a therapy is available to patients with various

types of cancer. It involves compensation of genetic defects through introducing proper DNA sequences and the silencing of those genes whose protein products are harmful to the body. Unlike chemotherapy and radiotherapy, this method is targeted at specific DNA fragments, individually for each patient. It does not consist in the destruction of all cells, including cancer ones, but in the precise reconstruction of the cancer-causing damage [11].

4. Summary

Analysing the cases described in historical and contemporary records, one can notice a significant change in the perception and management of cancer patients. Over the years, the protocol for cancer management has changed and, moreover, attention has been given to the fact that cancer is not a disease that should always be treated in the same manner. Scientists are still trying to explain the cause of cancers, amongst others, by examining human remains preserved for hundreds or even thousands of years. Nowadays, patients receive a holistic approach, with attention being paid to both their physical and mental well-being. Furthermore, the Quick Oncological Therapy programme has been created, which – to a certain degree – facilitates the patient's diagnosis. As the number of cancer patients is increasing each year, this issue deserves an in-depth analysis. Stress must be placed on what has the most beneficial influence on cancer patients and when it is forbidden to work with a given patient (e.g. what kind of rehabilitation should be avoided) – according to the *primum non nocere* (first, do no harm) principle.

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Corresponding Author:
Paulina Zachara-Kierońska

Address:
Al. Artura Grottgera 1, 18-400 Kraków

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